

Self-propelled Janus platinum mesoporous-silica nanoparticles for enhanced endodontic treatment

ABSTRACT

Biofilms contribute to the development of various oral diseases, particularly endodontic infections. The challenges posed by the intricate anatomy of root canals and the resilience of these infections to antimicrobials require innovative treatment strategies to improve endodontic outcomes. This study introduces a novel approach using self-propelled Janus platinum-mesoporous silica nanoparticles (i.e. nanomotors), loaded with chlorhexidine (CHX) and functionalized with a pH-dependent molecular gate bound to a ficin protease, which acts as an enzymatic drill. These multifunctional nanomotors combine unique properties to eliminate biofilms derived from the oral cavity, including H₂O₂-triggered movement, biofilm matrix degradation, and controlled CHX release at acidic pH. The effectiveness of the nanomotors against saliva-derived and root canal biofilms was demonstrated.

Notably, H₂O₂-activated nanomotors carrying a low concentration of CHX -ten times lower than conventional commercial formulations- exhibited a strong antimicrobial effect on oral biofilms, whereas CHX alone showed minimal impact. Moreover, the nanomotors disrupted mature *Streptococcus mutans* biofilms on dentine sections. In addition, the nanodevices effectively penetrated dentinal microtubules, eradicating bacterial biofilms residing within them, thereby underscoring the efficiency of this approach in clinically relevant oral environments. Collectively, these findings suggest that H₂O₂-activated nanomotors loaded with CHX represent a promising treatment strategy for endodontic infections. Their ability to deliver antimicrobial agents in a controlled manner and to reach challenging microenvironments could significantly enhance treatment outcomes of these persistent infections. This approach may serve as an effective complementary therapy in endodontic care, addressing the limitations of current sterilization methods.

Introduction

Biofilms can be described as complex microbial communities that can firmly adhere to both biotic and abiotic surfaces and are encased in a self-produced macromolecular matrix that shields them from external factors [11,33]. The ability of various bacteria to form biofilms is closely associated with the onset, progression, and persistence of oral diseases, including dental caries, periodontitis, and particularly endodontic infections [17,32,51]. These infections, which affect the pulp tissues, pose a significant challenge in dentistry and oral health. Alarmingly, the World Health Organization (WHO) ranks endodontic-related infections as the fourth most costly pathology in terms of direct treatment expenses [35].

One of the primary obstacles in managing endodontic infections is the complex anatomy of root canals. The intricate network of narrow, microscopic channels within the tooth significantly hinders the effectiveness of conventional instruments and drugs in reaching and successfully eliminating these biofilm-associated infections. For instance, approximately 47% of the canal walls will remain uninstrumented, and this percentage will rise to 72.9% in the apical third of the tooth [28]. Consequently, chemical treatment must compensate for the limitations of mechanical instrumentation in addressing the infected root canal system. However, this anatomical complexity fosters an ideal environment for the persistence of endodontic biofilms, which exhibit remarkable resilience and often resist conventional disinfectants and antibiotics, leading to treatment failures [4,38,47].

Several chemical agents have been proposed to address endodontic infections, involving irrigation agents such as sodium hypochlorite (NaClO), chlorhexidine (CHX) and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), as well as various interappointment medicaments such as calcium hydroxide and antibiotic pastes [6,27]. Although these agents offer some efficacy, they also present significant limitations. For example, NaClO can cause tissue irritation, and the widespread use of antibiotics can contribute to the emergence of antibiotic-resistant strains [8,29]. Additionally, CHX was found to be incapable of penetrating into deep biofilm layers [49]. Consequently, despite ongoing advancements in endodontic treatment, failure rates remain significant, with as many as 39% of treated teeth still showing evidence of apical periodontitis [39]. This underscores the urgent need for innovative strategies to combat endodontic infections [26].

Recent advancements in nanotechnology have demonstrated the potential of nanomaterials as powerful tools in the biomedical field, from diagnostics to drug delivery, disease prevention, and treatment. In particular, nanoparticles endowed with active motion (known as nanomotors) have emerged as ideal candidates for treating bacterial biofilms [19,50]. Through the combination of their nanometric size and the transformation of chemical substances or physical fields into kinetic energy, the nanomotors obtain the required driving force to overcome the physical barrier generated by the biofilm matrix. They can then eliminate bacteria using several improved strategies, such as administration of antibiotics or other antimicrobials, photothermal therapy (PTT) or photodynamic therapy (PDT), among others [45]. Given the good results exhibited by self-propelled nanoparticles in simplified environments, they have recently been applied for the treatment of biofilms responsible for endodontic infections. In this regard, Dasgupta et al. described a magnetically propelled silica-iron nanohelix capable of penetrating root canals and causing *Enterococcus faecalis* cell death by hyperthermia [12]. In addition, Wang et al. developed a dual-fueled nanomotor based on a metal-organic framework for the treatment of pulpitis [43]. The driving force of the nanodevice was first provided by the generation of nitric oxide (NO) and later by the decomposition of calcium dioxide (CaO₂) in the pathogenic acidic microenvironment, thereby killing bacteria collected from root canals with pulpitis and tested in rat models. To date, these nanotechnologies have exhibited the deepest root canal penetration, revealing the great ability of nanomotors to reach and remove oral biofilms. However, despite their advantages, these nano-designs have been unable to fully disrupt the biofilm matrix or effectively control the delivery of antimicrobial compounds to target infection sites.

Based on the above, we explore in this manuscript the application of a multifunctional nanomotor for targeting and treating endodontic infections. It is based on Janus nanoparticles composed of platinum nanoparticles (Pt) and mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN) combined in a single nanodevice (Janus Pt-MSN) [50]. The Pt face provides the propulsive element by catalyzing the decomposition of H₂O₂ (l) into O₂ (g), while the MSN face acts as a nanocontainer for CHX. Moreover, the MSN face is functionalized with a molecular gate formed by a supra-molecular complex constituted between benzimidazole groups (attached to the surface of the MSNs) and β -cyclodextrins (bound to the protease ficin). The molecular gate plays a dual role. On the one hand, it hydrolyzes the protein component of the biofilm matrix through the action of ficin, which works as a molecular drill. This, combined with the active motion, allows deep penetration of the nanomotor within the biofilm. On the other hand, it induces the specific release of CHX at acidic pH inside the biofilm, leading to biofilm eradication by killing the bacteria responsible for its formation (Fig. 1).

The antimicrobial abilities of a similar nanomotor to that reported herein in eradicating in vitro biofilms have been validated in our pre-vios work. We developed and evaluated self-propelled nanoparticles loaded with the antibiotic vancomycin to target *Staphylococcus aureus* biofilms associated with acute and chronic infections, achieving sub-stantial biofilm eradication [50]. This innovative nanodevice demon-strated a markedly enhanced efficacy over vancomycin alone, resulting in a drastic reduction of biomass and viability in both pre-formed and mature biofilms. Building on this foundation, the current manuscript explores the development and testing of hydrogen peroxide-activated gated Janus nanoparticles loaded with CHX for the targeted treatment of oral biofilms, particularly those linked to endodontic infections. This innovative approach aims to address conventional treatments' limitations and improve endodontic therapies' success rates by enhancing penetration into deeper regions of infected root canals. By targeting multispecies oral biofilms derived from saliva and endodontic in-fectons, as well as by testing penetration of the nanomotors in dentinal tubules to eliminate the bacterial biofilms residing within, our study evaluates the potential of this technology as a transformative strategy to improve oral biofilm eradication.

1. Results

1.1. Synthesis and characterization of CHX-loaded nanoparticles (NM_{CHX-F})

To reach the infected sites within the root canals and enhance the penetration of antimicrobial agents through the endodontic biofilm matrix, we decided to use Janus Pt-MSN nanomotors (NMs) as vehicles due to their well-demonstrated abilities. In summary, the Pt face of these nanodevices provides active motion by catalyzing the decomposition of H_2O_2 into O_2 (gas) and H_2O (liquid), thanks to its large and rough cat-alytic surface area. In addition, the MSN face offers a high loading ca-pacity and the possibility of external functionalization with molecular gates (also known as gatekeepers) to control cargo release. Herein, we loaded the broad-spectrum antiseptic chlorhexidine (CHX) and attached a pH-sensitive inclusion complex composed of benzimidazole molecules (BNZ) covalently bound to the nanomotor surface (NM_{BNZ}) and β -cy-clodextrins (β CDs) decorating a ficin enzyme (F- β CDs), which degrades the biofilm matrix acting as a molecular drill. NMs were prepared as previously described [50]. The protocol followed to obtain the final nanomotor NM_{CHX-F} (NM_{BNZ} loaded with CHX and functionalized with F- β CDs) is illustrated in Fig. 2a. To enable mechanistic interpretation, control nanoparticles lacking key functional components were also prepared: i.e. nanoparticles without CHX (NM_F , unable to trigger bac-terial death) and nanoparticles lacking ficin (NM_{CHX} , unable to degradethe biofilm matrix). For visualization studies, a fluorescently labeled analogue of the nanomotor was prepared using fluorescein isothiocyana-te (FITC) ($NM_{FITC-CHX-F}$). A summary of all synthesized nanomaterials is shown in Table S1.

The correct synthesis of NM_{CHX-F} was confirmed by multiple nano-material characterization techniques. Scanning transmission electron microscopy coupled with electronic energy-dispersive X-ray spectros-copy (STEM-EDX) analysis, shown in Fig. 2b, revealed that NM_{CHX-F} presents two faces of Pt (yellow) and silica (Si and O atoms represented in green and red, respectively). In addition,

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of the two-step strategy of Janus Pt-MSN nanomotors for the treatment of endodontic infections. Step 1: the combination of H_2O_2 -triggered movement and enzymatic degradation of biofilm matrix by ficin allows deep penetration into biofilms. Step 2: the specific release of CHX at an acidic pH causes bacterial death within the biofilm. The enhanced permeability of the nanomotors combined with the broad-spectrum antibacterial property of the antiseptic achieves effective elimination of the deep-seated bacteria embedded within biofilms responsible for endodontic infections. Schematic representation of the components that constitute the Janus Pt-MSN nanomotor: Janus Pt-MSN (composed of mesoporous silica and platinum), chlorhexidine (CHX), β -cyclodextrins, and ficin.

Fig. 2. Structural characterizations of chlorhexidine-loaded nanomotors functionalized with ficin (NM_{CHX-F}). **a** Schematic of the NM_{CHX-F} synthetic procedure described in Materials and Methods Section. **b** Elemental mapping of NM_{CHX-F} indicating the presence of O₂ (red, 41.8%), Si (green, 22.4%), Pt, (yellow, 24.2%), N (blue, 9.8%) and Cl (pink, 1.8%) atoms. This analysis was conducted by electron microscopy coupled with electronic energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (STEM-EDX) using a JEM 2100F instrument. **c** FTIR spectrum of NM (blue) and NM_{CHX-F} (purple). **d** XPS spectra of NM_{CHX-F} showing the following spectral characteristic signals: Si 2p (i); Pt 4f (ii); O 1s (iii); C 1s (iv); N 1s (v); and Cl 2p (vi). XPS measurements were collected with a Thermo Scientific X-ray photoelectron spectrometer, model K-alpha compact XPS, by using a nonmonochromatic Al K α (1486.6 eV) X-ray source and working at a base pressure of $4 \cdot 10^{-9}$ mBar. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the functionalization with ficin, and Cl atoms (pink) attributed to CHX were also detected.

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra (Fig. 2c and S1) provided direct evidence for the successful functionalization of the nanomotor. The spectrum of the base nanomotor (NM, blue) displayed the characteristic bands of the silica framework (Fig. 2c). After functionalization (NM_{CHX-F}, purple), these silica signatures: Si-O-Si stretching (1237 and 1077 cm⁻¹), Si-OH bending (806 cm⁻¹), and SiO₄ tetrahedral vibrations (954 cm⁻¹) remained intact, confirming the preservation of the inorganic matrix. In particular, the Si-O-Si stretching region (1150–1000cm⁻¹) became broader and more asymmetric after functionalization, consistent with the overlap of the silica framework vibrations and the C-O-C stretching modes of the β CD glycosidic units. The presence of ficin was evidenced by the appearance of the amide I band at 1652 cm⁻¹ and an attenuated amide II band at 1534 cm⁻¹, indicating that the protein retained its essential secondary structural integrity after immobilization. A weak band observed around 2980–3000 cm⁻¹ can be mainly attributed to aliphatic C-H stretching vibrations from the protein moiety. Furthermore, the attenuation of the broad O-H/N-H stretching band

(~3500–3100 cm^{-1}) in the final material, relative to the native components (Fig. S1), indicates the restriction of these bonds due to the supramolecular host-guest assembly between the F- β CD conjugate and the benzimidazole-functionalized MSN surface.

This spectroscopic evidence was complemented by quantitative and surface analysis. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA, Fig. S2) quantified a surface grafting density of 49 μg for the F- β CD molecular gate and a CHX payload of 170 μg per mg of $\text{NM}_{\text{CHX-F}}$. Furthermore, zeta potential measurements tracked the surface charge evolution: from -30 mV for the initial NM (due to silanol groups) to $+14.8$ mV for $\text{NM}_{\text{CHX-F}}$, a shift consistent with the isoelectric point of the surface-immobilized ficin (~ 9) (Fig. S3).

To complete the structural characterization of $\text{NM}_{\text{CHX-F}}$, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) studies were performed (Fig. 2d). The XPS spectra showed characteristic signals of Si, Pt, O, C, N, and Cl corresponding to the successful construction of the nanomotor. The Si 2p (Fig. 2d-i) spectrum displayed the characteristic $\text{Si}2p_{3/2}$ and $\text{Si}2p_{1/2}$ spin-orbit doublet states separated by approximately 0.6–0.7 eV [5]. The Si2p envelope did not significantly change throughout the successive functionalization steps from the NM solid to the final $\text{NM}_{\text{CHX-F}}$ (Table S2 and Fig. S4a). The Pt spectrum (Fig. 2d-ii) presented 2 intense peaks at 70.78 and 74.13 eV, attributed to the Pt $4f_{7/2}$ and $4f_{5/2}$ spin-orbit states of metallic Pt(0) [23]. Detailed deconvolution revealed 2 lower-intensity signals at 72.50 and 76.00 eV, assigned to the Pt $4f_{7/2}$ and Pt $4f_{5/2}$ levels of Pt(II) ($\sim 11\%$ relative to Pt(0)) (Megdalia et al., 2025), not show in NM (Fig. S4b). This partial oxidation of Pt occurs during BNZ incorporation and is maintained in subsequent functionalization stages (Table S2). In addition, PtO was also corroborated by a distinct component at 531.42 eV in the O1s spectrum (Fig. 2d-iii), while the dominant peak at 532.62 eV, corresponding to the silica network (Si-O-Si) [5]; Megdalia et al., 2025), remained unchanged throughout the functionalization steps. The O1s signal at ca. 531 eV begins to be detected in NM with a very low intensity of around 2%, increasing clearly up to a 13% when BNZ is incorporated. The signal at 531.5 eV was also indicative of the incorporation of organic components of the

Fig. 3. Functional characterizations of $\text{NM}_{\text{CHX-F}}$. a-i Normalized controlled release of CHX from $\text{NM}_{\text{CHX-F}}$, triggered by the pH-induced disassembly of the benzimidazole/ β -cyclodextrin molecular gate. Determined by UV-vis spectroscopy ($\lambda_{\text{em}} = 230$ nm) at neutral (7.5, black) and acidic pH (5, purple) (data expressed as mean \pm SD, $n = 3$). a-ii Zeta potential (mV) of $\text{NM}_{\text{CHX-F}}$ at pH 7.5 (black) and 5 (purple), (data expressed as mean \pm SD, $n = 3$). b $\text{NM}_{\text{CHX-F}}$ motion analysis. From left to right: mean square displacement (MSD) vs time interval ($\Delta t = 1$ s) in the presence and absence of H_2O_2 (from 0.075 to 0.2%) (i), diffusion coefficient (D_{eff} , $\mu\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$) at each fuel concentration (expressed as mean \pm SEM, $n = 20$ nanomotors) (ii) and representative spatial trajectories ($n = 5$) at 0 and 0.2% of H_2O_2 (iii). Statistics were performed by one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test, **** $p < 0.0001$. c Time-lapse images showing the generation of O_2 bubbles by $\text{NM}_{\text{CHX-F}}$ only 20 s after the addition of 0.2% H_2O_2 (indicated with an arrow). Scale bar, 1 cm. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

molecular gate (F- β CD), showing an increase in its intensity (27%) compared to NM_{BENZ} (13%) (Fig. S4c) due to the contribution of C–O groups of the ficin [3]. The successful anchoring of the F- β CD complex was further corroborated by the C1s and N1s spectra. The C1s spectrum (Fig. 2d-iv) showed three components at 284.80, 286.08, and 287.98 eV, attributed to CH/CH₂, CN/CS, and C–O groups, respectively [3,20]. All three components were detected from the early stages of functionalization (Table S2), with a particular signal enhancement at 287.98 eV in the final material attributed to the abundance of carbonyl groups originating from ficin. Concurrently, the evolution of the N1s spectrum (Fig. 2d-v) confirms the functionalization sequence. The initial anchoring of benzimidazole is evidenced by the doublets at 399.60 eV (pyrrolic N) and 401.00 eV (pyridinic N) [20] (Fig. S4d). Subsequent to the binding of F- β CD, there is a significant decrease in the relative intensity of the N-pyridine peak (11%), attributable to an increase in the signal at ca. 399.6 eV. This is associated with the incorporation of a high number of NH groups present in ficin [20], thereby supporting the formation of an inclusion complex with benzimidazole groups. Finally, CHX loading was unambiguously confirmed by the appearance of a Cl2p spin-orbit doublet in the XPS spectrum (Fig. 2d-vi). The spectrum was resolved into two distinct chlorine species, evidenced by two pairs of signals at 201.93/200.93 eV and 199.27/197.63 eV, corresponding to the Cl2p_{1/2} and Cl2p_{3/2} spin-orbit states [30].

Further, the ability of NM_{CHX-F} to release CHX in response to pH conditions mimicking those of oral biofilms (i.e. acidic pH) was evaluated. UV-vis spectroscopy results, depicted in Fig. 3a-i, indicated that at neutral pH (7.5, black), CHX remained encapsulated, while at acidic pH characteristic of biofilms (5, purple), the antiseptic was preferentially released to the media due to the disassembly of the molecular gate formed by the benzimidazole/F- β CD inclusion complex. This process was initiated by the protonation of the benzimidazole groups (pK_a = 5.55) [18] that decorate the MSN surface of the nanomotor. To investigate this mechanism, zeta potential measurements were performed for NM_{CHX-F} at both pH 7.5 (black) and pH 5 (purple) (Fig. 3a-ii). The surface charge increased from 14.8 mV at pH 7.5 to 24.2 mV at pH 5, consistent with the protonation of the benzimidazole groups. Consequently, the formation constant of benzimidazole/F- β CD inclusion complex decreased from 104 \pm 8 M⁻¹ (K _{β CD-BENZ}) to 42 \pm 12 M⁻¹ (K _{β CD-BENZ+}), leading to complex dissociation [48]. As a result, the MSN pores were opened, thus enabling the CHX release into the medium according to the concentration gradient [1,21].

Next, the capacity of NM_{CHX-F} to move in response to the catalytic decomposition of H₂O₂ was investigated. In the context of nanoscale catalytic motors, active motion is usually manifested as an increase in the diffusion coefficient (D, defined by the Stokes-Einstein equation, Eq. 1) [9,44]. To assess this phenomenon, nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA) using a Nanosight NS300 instrument was performed. The equipment recorded 30 s videos of the nanomotors in the presence of different H₂O₂ concentrations (from 0 to 0.2%), from which the x and y positions of each individual nanoparticle were extracted. These co-ordinates were used to calculate their mean square displacement (MSD, Eq. 2), and plotting the MSD vs time intervals (Δt) allowed determination of the diffusion coefficient (Eq. 3). Upon fuel catalysis, the slope of the MSD vs Δt plot increases, in accordance with an enhancement of D₀ (diffusion coefficient in the absence of fuel), referred to as effective diffusion coefficient (D_{eff}).

As observed in Fig. 3b-i, the MSD presented a linear correlation with Δt at all the H₂O₂ concentrations evaluated (from 0.075 to 0.2%), with the slope progressively increasing with fuel concentration. Furthermore, NM_{CHX-F} in the absence of H₂O₂ showed a D₀ of 1.06 \pm 0.12 $\mu\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$, which is similar to the theoretical value (1.1 $\mu\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$, Eq. 1) for nanoparticles of these dimensions (267 \pm 23 nm). In contrast, D_{eff} increased from 2.4 \pm 0.1 $\mu\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$ at 0.075% to 6.6 \pm 0.2 $\mu\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$ at H₂O₂ 0.2% (Fig. 3b-ii).

To further characterize the motion, the anomalous diffusion exponent (α) of NM_{CHX-F} was derived from the slope of the log-log plot of

MSD vs Δt . An α value near 1 indicates Brownian motion, while $\alpha > 1$ signifies active motion (also referred to as superdiffusion) [46]. As shown in Fig. S5, the non-fueled nanomotors exhibited an α of 0.72 \pm 0.21, whereas upon the addition of 0.2% H₂O₂, α increased to 1.23 \pm

0.17. These significant enhancements in both D_{eff} and α coefficients in the presence of H₂O₂ demonstrated the active motion of NM_{CHX-F}. The trajectories of the fueled nanomotors, which exhibited random behavior with a longer reach compared to their trajectories in PBS, also confirmed the increased diffusion of NM_{CHX-F} (Fig. S6 and Fig. 3b-iii).

The propulsion of the nanomotors was driven by the formation, growth, stabilization, and collapse of O₂ bubbles on its Pt face, as observed with the naked eye (Fig. 3c). This bubble-propulsion mechanism resulted from the anisotropic structure of the nanomaterial (Janus Pt-MSN dimer) and the rough Pt surface with high catalytic activity toward H₂O₂ decomposition [13,14]. Moreover, we investigated the dispersion dynamics of nanomotors population in the presence of the fuel. After adding a drop of NM_{CHX-F} to a solution containing H₂O₂, the nanodevices rapidly dispersed and migrated away from the initial addition point. The global dispersal of the nanomotor population was quantified by the increase in the area occupied by them and the spread of pixel intensity from the initial addition point toward the periphery over time (Fig. S7), which reflected enhanced, non-coordinated dispersion. Conversely, in the absence of H₂O₂, the nanomotors remained aggregated near the addition point.

These findings confirmed that the nanomotor is able to perform the tasks potentially required to treat endodontic infections: its H₂O₂-triggered self-propulsion could provide penetration through the complex anatomy of root canals and biofilm matrix. At the same time, its ability to deliver CHX specifically at acidic pH could lead to the elimination of the bacteria embedded within it.

1.2. Effect of NM_{CHX-F} on disrupting biofilms derived from saliva

Firstly, the anti-biofilm and antibacterial activity of NM_{CHX-F} was assessed on multispecies biofilms derived from saliva samples. To this end, unstimulated whole saliva biofilms were grown and exposed to various treatments: NM_{CHX-F} activated with H₂O₂, non-propelled NM_{CHX-F}, the fuel that induces the propulsion (H₂O₂), CHX (at the same concentration encapsulated in the nanomotor), all the components of the final nanosystem but unassembled and in the presence of the fuel (NA + H₂O₂), and control nanoparticles deprived of one of their essential components, i.e. ficin (NM_{CHX}) or CHX (NM_F) in the presence of fuel.

The effect of nanomotor and the different controls on the saliva-derived biofilm biomass was evaluated by crystal violet staining (CV). As shown in Fig. 4a, biofilms treated with 0.02% CHX (a concentration 10 times lower than commercially available products; [16,34]) showed no effect on the biofilm biomass compared to the untreated control. This was likely due to the lack of efficient penetration of CHX through the biofilm matrix. In contrast, NM_{CHX-F} displayed significant anti-biofilm activity, eradicating up to 40% of the biofilm even without activation of their self-propelled motion using H₂O₂. This observation highlights the strong synergy between the CHX, the proteolytic activity of ficin and the nanoparticle delivery system. The biofilm eradication effect was further enhanced to

69% when the nanomotors were activated with 0.15% of H_2O_2 . Furthermore, the treatment with either H_2O_2 alone, the disassembled nanoparticle components with H_2O_2 (NA + H_2O_2) or the fueled control nanoparticles NM_{CHX} and NM_F (Fig. S8) had no impact on biofilm mass, confirming that the observed anti-biofilm effect is specifically attributed to the combined action of all the nanomotor active components (CHX and ficin) fully assembled in a Janus nanoparticle along with its autonomous movement.

To aid interpretation of the crystal violet assay results, it should be noted that the visual appearance of CV-stained wells reflects only the residual dye remaining on the bottom surface after washing, whereas the quantitative absorbance values correspond to the total solubilized CV

Fig. 4. Effect of nanomotors on saliva-derived biofilms (a-c) and on oral biofilms derived from endodontic root canal infections (d). a Biomass of saliva-derived biofilms evaluated by measuring the absorbance of released CV after treatment with the activated nanomotors ($NM_{CHX-F} + H_2O_2$), non-activated nanomotors (NM_{CHX-F}), hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), 0.02% chlorhexidine (CHX), and non-assembled nanoparticles (all elements used for CHX-loaded nanoparticle synthesis + H_2O_2 , NA). Left: absorbance of released CV. Right: representative images of the biofilms, from top to bottom: $NM_{CHX-F} + H_2O_2$, NM_{CHX-F} , H_2O_2 , CHX, NA and control. Biofilms derived from the saliva samples of six volunteers were grown for 24 h and treated for 24 h. Data are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 6$). b Viability of saliva-derived biofilms evaluated by LIVE/DEAD assay after treatment with $NM_{CHX-F} + H_2O_2$. b-i Representative CLSM images showing SYTO9-labeled cells in green and propidium iodide-labeled cells in red (merged). Scale bar: 100 μ m. b-ii Quantification of viable cells. Data are presented as mean \pm SEM ($n = 3$). c-i 3D reconstruction of saliva-derived biofilm matrix after treatment with FITC-labeled nanomotors ($NM_{FITC-CHX-F} + H_2O_2$), showing biofilm biomass stained with Alexa Fluor 680-dextran conjugate (red) and nanomotors (green). c-ii $NM_{FITC-CHX-F}$ distribution over biofilm sections from 5 to 40 μ m. d Disruption of endodontic biofilm biomass evaluated by measuring absorbance of released CV. Left: absorbance of released CV. Right: representative images of the biofilms. Biofilms derived from patient endodontic samples collected from six participants were grown for 8 h and treated with $NM_{CHX-F} + H_2O_2$, NM_{CHX-F} , H_2O_2 , 0.2% CHX, and NA + H_2O_2 for 8 h. Data are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 6$). Statistical significance was assessed using Student's *t*-test, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, p**** < 0.0001 , compared to control.

retained across the entire well, including biofilm distributed on the sidewalls. Treatments such as H₂O₂ can induce partial detachment and collapse of the biofilm, leading to dense residual patches that retain CV strongly and appear as dark localized regions, despite a reduction in overall biomass (da Cruz Nizer et al., 2024). Because the CV microtiter-plate assay is highly sensitive to heterogeneity in staining, washing, and biomass distribution, spectrophotometric quantification of solubilized CV is considered the most reliable indicator of total biofilm biomass (Stepanović et al., 2000; Skogman et al., 2012). Accordingly, the quantitative absorbance values represent the definitive measure of treatment efficacy.

Once the ability of the nanomotor to disrupt the biofilm matrix was established, we next evaluated its bactericidal activity using a LIVE/DEAD assay by confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM). This method allows the detection of total DNA (stained in green) and DNA from cells with damaged membranes (stained in red) within the biofilm. Notably, saliva-derived biofilms contain a complex community of different bacterial species together with debris from the oral mucosa, which can contribute to an elevated apparent basal level of cell death. Therefore, to accurately quantify the treatment-induced cytotoxicity, viable cells were determined by subtracting red signal from green signal. The results, shown in Fig. 4b, indicate that treatment with NM_{CHX-F} in the presence of the fuel caused a significant decrease in viable cells, corresponding to a 94% reduction relative to the control. This confirms that the nanomotor had a remarkable bactericidal effect in multispecies saliva-derived biofilms, which is attributed to the local pH-triggered release of CHX.

In a further step, the biofilm penetration ability of the nanomotor along with its EPS-degrading activity was assessed by CLSM. To do so, the biofilm matrix was stained with Alexa Fluor 680-dextran conjugate (red), whereas the nanomotor was labeled with fluorescein (NM_{FITC-CHX-F}, green), and a 3D reconstruction of the biofilm was generated. As illustrated in Fig. 4c-i and Fig. S9 treatment with the fueled nanomotor induced a remarkable disruption of the biofilm matrix, quantified as a 95% reduction in biofilm biomass based on EPS-related fluorescence compared to the control (Fig. S9a), and as almost 60% reduction in total biofilm thickness (decreasing from 90 μm in the control to 40 μm in the nanomotor-treated samples, Fig. S9b). Moreover, the spatial distribution of NM_{FITC-CHX-F} (labeled nanomotor) within the biofilm was assessed by quantifying the fluorescence across biofilm cross-sections (depths from 5 to 40 μm, Fig. 4c-ii). Nanoparticles were detected throughout the entire biofilm thickness. Although the fluorescence signal reached its maximum in the central region (approximately 20–25 μm corresponding to nearly half the total biofilm thickness), a significant signal was also measured in both the upper layers and, more importantly, in the deeper inner layers, confirming extensive infiltration. These data demonstrate that nanomotors effectively penetrate the biofilm structure, consistent with their enhanced diffusivity and EPS-degrading activity.

Overall, these findings demonstrate the mechanistic efficacy of NM_{CHX-F} and indicate that a self-propelling nanomotor combining proteolytic matrix degradation with targeted CHX delivery offers a powerful tool against complex oral multispecies biofilms.

1.3. Eradication of *in vitro* patient-derived endodontic biofilms

We further investigated NM_{CHX-F} efficacy against biofilms isolated from infected root canals of patients undergoing endodontic treatment. These biofilms were cultured *in vitro* mimicking the complex bacterial composition within the root canal [41] and exposed to the same treatment regimens as saliva-derived biofilms mentioned above. However, considering the initial ineffectiveness of free 0.02% CHX observed on saliva-derived biofilms, the concentration of both free and nanoparticle-encapsulated CHX was increased to 0.2%. CV staining results (Fig. 4d) revealed that CHX at this higher concentration achieved a significant biofilm disruption effect (*p*-value = 0.01), similar to that observed with non-activated nanoparticles (NM_{CHX-F}) (*p*-value = 0.0063). Nevertheless, when nanomotor's movement was activated using H₂O₂, they demonstrated a significantly enhanced ability to eradicate biofilms, achieving over 85% removal of complex endodontic biofilms (*p*-value = 0.0007). In contrast, as observed in the experiments with saliva-derived biofilms, the treatment with H₂O₂ or unassembled nanoparticles + H₂O₂ had no effect on biofilm biomass. Thus, the synergistic effect associated to EPS (extracellular polymeric substances) disruption by ficin enzymatic activity and nanomotor's active motion appears to play a crucial role in the nanodevice's efficacy against endodontic biofilms.

1.4. Eradication of mature *S. mutans* biofilms on dentine discs

Following the assessment of NM_{CHX-F} against multispecies oral biofilms (both saliva and root canal endodontic infections), their efficacy against mature biofilms grown on dentine discs – as a more clinically relevant model – was investigated. *S. mutans* biofilms were cultivated on dentine discs for seven days prior to exposure to the designated treatments for one and five minutes. As depicted in Fig. 5a, treatment with CHX (0.2%) for one minute significantly reduced the viability of mature

S. mutans biofilm by over two orders of magnitude. This reduction was similar to that observed after mature biofilm exposure to H₂O₂-activated NM_{CHX-F}. Conversely, treatment with the non-motile nanoparticles (NM_{CHX-F}) also resulted in significant inhibition of mature biofilm viability, although to a lesser degree. This may be attributed to the limited action time available for the nanoparticles to penetrate the acidic biofilm matrix and release their therapeutic cargo. However, when *S. mutans* biofilms were treated for five minutes (Fig. 5b), a slight increase in the antibiofilm activity was observed in the group treated with non-activated nanoparticles (NM_{CHX-F}). This suggests that longer exposure times could result in more significant biofilm disaggregation. Notably, after five minutes of treatment, although a similar effect was observed with CHX (0.2%), the activated nanoparticles (NM_{CHX-F} + H₂O₂) completely eradicated the mature biofilms, demonstrating an exceptional capacity for penetration, disaggregation, and destruction of single-species biofilms grown on dentine sections. Additionally, the

control group (NA), in the presence of H₂O₂, exhibited a biofilm-killing efficacy comparable to CHX at five minutes. While H₂O₂ alone demonstrated no biofilm-killing or eradication capacity at one minute after treatment, it appeared to reduce viable counts at five minutes of treatment, (*p*-value = 0.008), although its effect was less than that of the control group (NA). These findings highlight the clear advantage of H₂O₂-activated, CHX-loaded nanoparticles in achieving superior biofilm eradication on a model mimicking the root canal surface.

1.5. Eradication of mature *S. mutans* biofilms on dentinal tubules

Besides the antimicrobial and biofilm-disrupting activity of the nanoparticles, which surpasses the effect of CHX alone, a key advantage of these nanoparticles is their inherent ability to move. This characteristic may be especially crucial for reaching and eradicating endodontic biofilms within the intricate anatomy of root canals, one of the most relevant factors responsible for endodontic

treatment failure [36]. Thus, to further evaluate their potential as a tool to treat endodontic in-fectons, we examined the ability of self-propelled NM_{CHX-F} to penetrate and eradicate biofilms within dental tubules- a complex environment that closely mimics the conditions contributing to infection resilience. For this purpose, *S. mutans* mature biofilms were grown within dental tubules for seven days and subsequently exposed to the designated treatments for five minutes (Fig. 5c-i). The effect on biofilm viability within dental tubules was then analyzed using CLSM (Fig. 5c-ii). The results revealed that CHX (0.2%) was unable to eliminate the bacteria embedded within the biofilm residing inside the dental tubules. Similarly, neither 0.15% H_2O_2 nor NA displayed any significant effect on these deeply embedded biofilms. However, a notable increase in dead bacterial cells within the tubules was observed when the dentine spec-imens were treated with NM_{CHX-F} compared to previous treatments. This

Fig. 5. Effect of nanomotors on the viability of mature *S. mutans* biofilms. *S. mutans* biofilms were grown on dentine disks for 7 days and then treated with activated nanomotors ($NM_{CHX-F} + H_2O_2$), non-activated nanomotors (NM_{CHX-F}), 0.2% chlorhexidine (CHX), hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), and non-assembled nanoparticles (all elements used for CHX-loaded nanoparticle synthesis + H_2O_2 - NA). Following treatment, biofilm viability was assessed by

CFU count at 1 min (a) or 5 min (b). Data are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 7$). Statistical significance was assessed using Student's test. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. c Evaluation of nanomotors on

S. mutans biofilm eradication within dental tubes. c-i Schematic illustration of the experimental design. *S. mutans* biofilms were cultured within dental tubules for

7 days. Subsequently, biofilms were treated for 5 min with activated nanomotors (NM_{CHX-F} + H₂O₂), non-activated nanomotors (NM_{CHX-F}), 0.2% chlorhexidine (CHX), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), and non-assembled nanoparticles (all elements used for CHX-loaded nanoparticle synthesis + H₂O₂ - NA). c-ii Confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) micrographs following 5 min of indicated treatments. Scale bar, 25 μ m

suggests enhanced penetration and biofilm disruption by the nano-particles. Remarkably, when the nanomotors' motility was activated using H₂O₂, CLSM images revealed a virtually complete killing of bacterial cells from within the dental tubules.

To directly visualize and confirm the deep penetration capability of the nanomotor within dental tubules, we performed a focused ion beam scanning electron microscopy (FIB-SEM) analysis of the dental tubules treated with NM_{CHX-F} + H₂O₂. The SEM images, particularly those obtained using backscattered electron detection (BSE), which highlight high atomic elements like platinum (shown in white in the BSE images), unequivocally revealed activated NM_{CHX-F} distributed inside the dentine tubule. Nanomotors were directly

observed at depths up to

164 μ m from the canal entrance, reaching the maximum observed penetration depth of 344 μ m (Fig. 6). EDX spectroscopy further corroborated the presence of the nanomotors' constituent elements (Pt and Si), together with Ca and P atoms from the dentine matrix, within the dental tubules (Fig. S10).

This visual evidence directly correlates with the CLSM findings, confirming that H₂O₂-propelled, CHX-loaded nanoparticles possess the ability to penetrate intricate and challenging environments of root canal anatomy and exert their antimicrobial activity on the bacteria colonizing them.

2. Conclusion

Endodontic infections have long posed a persistent challenge in dental care, primarily due to the intricate anatomy of root canals and the resilience of biofilms. Despite advances in treatment protocols, the high prevalence of infection-related treatment failures [39] suggests that current therapies may not fully address all factors contributing to infection persistence [10]. Conventional treatments, including mechanical debridement and chemical irrigants, have their limitations,

Fig. 6. FIB-SEM visualization of nanomotor penetration into dentinal tubules. *S. mutans* biofilms were grown within dentinal tubules for 7 days and then treated with activated nanomotors (NM_{CHX-F} + H₂O₂) for 5 min. The images show representative areas where nanomotors were detected inside the dentinal tubules at increasing depths from: a canal entrance, b to 164 μm and c 344 μm (maximum depth observed). Left and center panels: secondary electron (SE) images. Right panels: backscattered electron (BSE) images, where the Pt of the nanomotors appears bright. Their penetration into dentinal tubes is indicated by arrows in the low magnification images (left).

especially when it comes to completely eliminating biofilms, which are often deeply embedded within root canal complexities including the dentinal tubules. This research introduces a groundbreaking alternative: self-propelled Janus nanomotors loaded with CHX, which offer a more targeted and efficient method for the eradication of biofilm-related infections.

Current irrigation strategies include the use of irrigating solutions combined with activation or agitation to help them reach anatomical complexities. NaClO is the most popular irrigant due to its tissue-dissolving and bactericidal properties, establishing it as the “gold standard” irrigant for application between each file change [7,10]. Final irrigation with a chelating agent such as EDTA is required to facilitate the removal of the smear layer and dentine debris thereby enhancing final antimicrobial irrigant penetration [6]. CHX has also been proposed as a root canal irrigant because of its broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity and prolonged substantivity. However, it has several flaws such as reduced activity against biofilms as it cannot disrupt the EPS matrix [7], and lack of tissue dissolution capacity [25]. Additionally, CHX combination with NaClO or EDTA requires exhaustive rinsing to avoid undesirable precipitate formation. Furthermore, conventional irrigation methods using syringes and needles and activation/agitation techniques fail to adequately reach the entire root canal system, particularly the apical region, thereby limiting their efficacy. Consequently, new strategies to effectively remove root canal biofilms are required [6].

In this study, we introduce Janus nanomotors, a novel approach that overcomes the limitations of conventional irrigants by combining chemical disinfection with mechanical movement. The platinum face of the Janus nanomotor catalyzes the decomposition of H₂O₂, creating an active propulsion mechanism that allows the nanomotors to move through complex and narrow root canal system. This motion is critical for reaching areas that are typically inaccessible to files and irrigating solutions. The active movement of the nanomotors, coupled with the enzymatic activity of ficin—a protease that breaks down the biofilm matrix [52]—enables these nanomotors to penetrate biofilms and eliminate bacteria from deep within the dentinal tubules. Consistent with this, direct SEM analysis confirmed the presence of activated nanomotors within the dentinal tubule lumen at depths of 164 μm and, in some cases, up to 344 μm from the canal entrance. With an average diameter of approximately 267 nm, well below the typical diameter of dentinal tubules (0.5–3 μm), they are small enough to penetrate deeply into the tubule system and access embedded biofilms.

This ability to reach and disrupt biofilms in the intricate canal network, where conventional methods struggle, highlights the potential of Janus nanomotors as a transformative tool for endodontic care. We therefore suggest that nanomotors could be a suitable complementary treatment strategy to the current irrigation protocol. Sodium hypochlorite and EDTA act as effective debriding agents, while the Janus nanomotors deliver a powerful, targeted antibiofilm effect in difficult-to-reach areas. This dual strategy could significantly enhance treatment outcomes, ensuring that both the tissue and biofilm components of the infection are addressed thoroughly.

Importantly, the Janus nanomotors can be used at much lower concentrations of CHX compared to conventional methods, which minimizes the potential for cytotoxicity and systemic side effects while maintaining their antimicrobial efficacy [42]. Additionally, the controlled release of CHX within the acidic microenvironment of biofilms offers significant advantages over conventional irrigation as the acidic pH found in mature biofilms triggers the release of CHX from the nanomotor, ensuring that the drug is delivered directly to the infection site, optimizing the therapeutic effect.

One of the most promising aspects of Janus nanomotors is their versatility. While we focused on CHX for its broad-spectrum antibacterial activity, these nanomotors can be loaded with other antimicrobial agents, such as antibiotics, antiseptics, or even natural compounds. This flexibility makes them highly adaptable to a range of clinical needs and treatment protocols. For instance, in cases of antibiotic resistance, nanomotors could deliver novel or combination therapies in a controlled manner, potentially reducing the risk of resistance development by targeting biofilms more effectively than conventional methods.

When compared to other nanoparticle technologies for irrigation, such as titanium oxide nanoparticles (TiO₂-NPs) combined with UV radiation or silver nanoparticles (AgNPs), Janus nanomotors offer several key advantages. TiO₂-NPs, activated by UV light, generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) that exhibit antimicrobial effects; however, this method relies on light activation, which can be challenging to achieve consistently in the intricate, deep areas of root canals. Additionally, TiO₂-NPs have been shown to cause potential cytotoxicity and require careful management to avoid adverse effects [15]. On the other hand, AgNPs have demonstrated strong antimicrobial properties, capable of penetrating biofilms and killing a wide range of bacteria, including difficult-to-treat Gram-negative strains. However, high concentrations of AgNPs can be toxic to human cells [31], and, similarly to other irrigants, their effectiveness is compromised by their limited mobility within the root canal system.

In contrast, Janus nanomotors exhibit self-motility allowing them to navigate and actively target biofilm in complex canal areas. This unique movement combined with the enzymatic activity of ficin and the controlled, pH-sensitive release of CHX, enhances their penetration and bactericidal efficacy, even in hard-to-reach regions. This targeted approach not only improves biofilm disruption but also minimizes cytotoxicity risks by enabling effective treatment at significantly lower CHX concentrations. Nevertheless, the long-term

safety of Janus nano-motors remains an essential factor for their potential clinical adoption. While silica-based nanoparticles are generally recognized for their biocompatibility, the platinum component—necessary for catalytic movement—may present concerns if residual particles remain within the root canal. Although the application protocol is designed to wash out nanomotors after biofilm removal, further research on the in vivo safety of these materials is necessary to confirm that any remaining nano-particles do not accumulate to toxic levels. These studies are crucial to ensuring that Janus nanomotors maintain a favorable safety profile even with trace residuals, thereby supporting their use in clinical endodontic applications with minimal risks. For this study, *S. mutans* was selected due to its well-characterized and robust biofilm-forming capabilities. While *E. faecalis* is commonly associated with persistent root canal infections, recent microbiological studies report that it may account for a relatively low proportion of the microbial communities present in endodontic infections [41]. Consequently, future research should focus on developing more clinically relevant endodontic infection models that more closely mimic real clinical scenarios.

In conclusion, self-propelled, CHX-loaded Janus nanomotors may offer a revolutionary approach to endodontic therapy. By combining chemical disinfection and mechanical movement, they provide a highly effective strategy to the deep, persistent biofilm infections that compromise the periapical healing. As a complementary therapy to conventional irrigation methods, Janus nanomotors could enhance biofilm management and, therefore, improve the treatment outcome. Thanks to their versatility, controlled release mechanisms, and potential for customized treatments, they could be the future of endodontics, offering more effective, targeted, and safer solutions for biofilm-associated diseases.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Synthesis of mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs)

Firstly, 1 g of *n*-cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) was dissolved in deionized water (DI) (480 mL). Then, 2 M NaOH (3.5 mL) was added to increase the pH and the temperature increased to 80 °C. Next, tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) was added dropwise and the reaction was maintained under magnetic stirring for 2 h. The resultant solid was isolated by centrifugation, washed with DI to neutral pH and dried at 70 °C. Lastly, the solid was calcinated at 550 °C under oxidizing atmosphere for 5 h, yielding MSNs.

MSNs labeled with fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) were also prepared. To this end, 6.6 mg of FITC were mixed with 833 µL of (3-aminopropyl) triethoxysilane (APTES), and the reaction was stirred magnetically for 1 h. The resulting solution was then mixed with 4.167 mL of TEOS, and the previously described procedure for the synthesis of MSNs was followed. The surfactant was removed by acid extraction with

1.5 mL of HCl under reflux at 80 °C overnight, obtaining MSN_{FITC}.

3.2. Synthesis of platinum nanoparticles (Pt)

A mixture of 164 mg H₂PtCl₆ and 20 mg of polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) was prepared in DI (20 mL). Then, a 350 mg solution of ascorbic acid in DI (10 mL) was added dropwise to the H₂PtCl₆ solution. The reaction was magnetically stirred for 3 h at 55 °C. The colour change to black indicated the successful synthesis of Pt nanoparticles.

3.3. Synthesis of Janus Pt-MSN nanomotors (NMs)

MSNs and Pt were combined in a single nanodevice, Janus Pt-MSN (NM), by the next procedure. First, 180 mg of MSNs were dispersed in a 1 mM CTAB solution (10 mL in ethanol 6.7%). The mixture was heated at 75 °C and 1 g of paraffin wax was added. An Ultra-Turrax T-8 (IKA, Germany) was used for 10 min at 25000 rpm to homogenize the sample. To establish a Pickering emulsion, the solution was magnetically stirred for 1 h at 75 °C. Later, 3-mercaptopropyl trimethoxysilane (200 mL) and methanol (10 mL) were added, and the reaction was kept under magnetic stirring for 3 h. The resultant solid was centrifuged and washed with methanol. The mercapto-functionalized solid was dispersed in methanol (68 mL) and mixed with the previously prepared Pt nanoparticles (30 mL). The reaction was magnetically stirred for 24 h at room temperature. Finally, the solid was isolated by filtration, washed with chloroform and dried at 70 °C, yielding NM. The same protocol was followed using MSN_{FITC} as starting material, obtaining NM_{FITC}.

3.4. Synthesis of final nanomotor (NM_{CHX-F}) and control nanoparticles

For the synthesis of the final nanomotor (NM_{CHX-F}), the next steps were followed:

- Functionalization of NMs with benzimidazole groups (BNZ)

First, the outer surface of the mesoporous face of NM was functionalized with BNZ groups that will form inclusion complexes with ficin bound β-cyclodextrins (F-βCD) to generate the pH-sensitive molecular gate. To attach the BNZ groups to NM, their surface was previously decorated with iodine groups. For this purpose, 60 mg of NMs were suspended in 4 mL of acetonitrile (ACN) and treated with 60 µL of (3-iodopropyl) trimethoxysilane. The reaction was magnetically for 5.5 h. The product was isolated by centrifugation (13,500 rpm, 3 min) and washed with toluene three times. Next, a saturated solution of BNZ was then prepared by mixing 0.25 mg of BNZ with 990 µL of TEA and 20 mL of toluene. The mixture was heated at 80 °C until complete dissolution of the BNZ. After that, 10 mL of the solution was added over NM. The re-action was kept under magnetic stirring at 80 °C under refluxing conditions for 3 days. Finally, the solid was isolated by centrifugation, washed with toluene and dried, yielding NM_{BNZ}.

- Loading of NMs with CHX

NM pores were loaded with the antiseptic CHX. For this purpose, 40 mg of NMs modified with BNZ (NM_{BNZ}) were mixed with a concentrated solution of CHX (10 mg in 4 mL of a dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)/ phosphate buffered saline (PBS) mixture, 1:1). The reaction was kept under magnetic stirring at room temperature for 24 h. The solid was isolated by centrifugation (13,500 rpm, 3 min).

- Synthesis of F-βCD

For the binding of βCD to ficin, βCD previously modified with amino groups was used (βCD-NH₂) [40]. First, EDC/NHS chemistry was used to activate the acidic groups of the enzyme. For this purpose, 25 mg ficin was dissolved in 4 mL of PBS (100 mM, pH 7.5) and mixed with 25 mg EDC and 25 mg of NHS. The reaction was kept under magnetic stirring at 4 °C for 30 min. Subsequently, 13 mg of βCD-NH₂ were added, and the mixture was stirred magnetically for 24 h at 4 °C to generate amide bonds between the amino groups of βCD-NH₂ and the activated acidic groups of ficin. Finally, F-βCD was dialyzed using 3 kDa Amicon Ultra-05 centrifuge filtration units (13,500 rpm, 5 min) and washed 3 times with cold PBS.

- Functionalization of NMs with F-βCD

To construct the molecular gate constituted by the inclusion com-plexes established between the BNZ groups functionalizing the NMs surface and the ficin-bound βCD, 40 mg of NMs were mixed with 12.5 mg F-βCD in 3 mL of PBS. The reaction was stirred magnetically over-night at 4 °C. Finally, the mixture was centrifuged (13,500 rpm, 5 min) and the resulting solid was washed with PBS (100 mM, pH 7.5), yielding the final nanomotor NM_{CHX-F}.

For the synthesis of the final nanomotor labeled with FITC (NM_{FITC-CHX-F}), the same procedure was followed but using NM_{FITC} as starting material. Control nanoparticles lacking CHX (NM_F) or ficin (NM_{CHX}) were also prepared. To synthesize NM_F, 15 mg of NM_{BNZ} reacted with

3.75 mg of F-βCD in 3 mL of 100 mM PBS pH 7.5 overnight at 4 °C. For

the synthesis of NM_{CHX} 15 mg of CHX-loaded NM_{BNZ} reacted overnight with 5 mg of βCD in 3 mL of 100 mM PBS pH 7.5.

3.5. Cargo controlled-release experiments

To study the ability of NM_{CHX-F} to deliver CHX, controlled-release assays at different pH were performed. In a typical experiment, 2 sus-pensions of NM_{CHX-F} were prepared at a concentration of 0.5 mg/mL in PBS; in one tube, the pH was adjusted to 7.5 and in the other to 5. The mixtures were placed on a shaker (Thermo-shaker HC24N Grant In-struments, 14,000 rpm) at 37 °C and, at times of 0, 15, 30, 60, 90, 120 and 180 min, centrifuged to remove the nanodevices (13,500 rpm, 3 min). The resulting supernatant was filtered to remove traces of F-βCD present in the medium (centrifugation at 13,500 rpm for 3 min on 3 kDa Amicon Ultra-05 filters). Finally, the percentage of CHX released to the medium was determined by UV-visible spectroscopy (λ_{abs} = 230 nm). After the release assays, the samples containing nanoparticles were washed with water and analyzed to determine their zeta potential (mV) with a ZetaSizer Nano ZS (Malvern). The zeta potential of NM and NM_{BNZ} was also analyzed under the same conditions.

3.6. Analysis of nanomotors movement

The nanomotor's movement in response to H₂O₂ was evaluated by nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA) using the Nanosight NS300 (Mal-vern Panalytical). For this purpose, H₂O₂ solutions (concentrations from 0 to 0.2%, v/v) were first introduced into the chamber of the device to avoid drift. Then, a NM_{CHX-F} suspension was introduced in the system (concentration of 2 μg/mL in PBS) and 5 videos of 30 s were recorded. The NTA 3.0 software analyzed the spatial x and y coordinates of the nanoparticles recorded in the videos individually. Based on this infor-mation, an in-housed developed R code was used to calculate the mean square displacement (MSD) of each nanoparticle (Eq. 1). The diffusion coefficient (expressed as D_{eff} for nanomotors in the presence of fuel and D₀ for nanomotors in the absence of fuel) was obtained by plotting MSD vs Δt (1 s) and applying Eq. 2. The analysis was applied to a population

of 20 nanodevices with a size similar to that observed by dynamic light scattering (DLS). The α coefficient for each nanoparticle was calculated from the slope of the log-log plot of MSD vs Δt.

$$D = \frac{TK_B}{6\pi\eta R_h}$$

Equation 1. Stokes-Einstein equation. Where D is the diffusion co-efficient, η is the viscosity, K_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the tem-perature and R_h is the hydrodynamic radius.

$$\{ \dots \}_2 \quad \{ \dots \}_2$$

the laboratory for biofilm growth. In order to prioritize the preservation of biofilm bacterial diversity from endodontic root canal infection, samples were cultivated for 8 h in BHI medium supplemented with vitamin K1, hemin, and menadione; following the formulation used for saliva-derived biofilms. After 8 h of growth, biofilm derived from end-odontic samples underwent the designated treatment which included H₂O₂-activated nanoparticles (NM_{CHX-F} + 0.15% H₂O₂), reaching 0.2% of CHX, non-activated nanoparticles (NM_{CHX-F}), 0.15% H₂O₂, 0.2% CHX and the "unassembled device", and were grown for additional 24 h. Each experimental condition included two technical replicates along with corresponding negative controls.

$$MSD \equiv \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^N (x_i(t) - x_i(0))^2$$

Equation 2. Mean square displacement (MSD). Where x_i y x_t are the vector positions of the nanoparticles at different times and N is the average number of nanoparticles.

$$MSD = 4D_0\Delta t$$

$$MSD = 4D_{eff}\Delta t$$

Equation 3. Diffusion coefficient (D). Where MSD is the mean square displacement, D₀ is the diffusion coefficient in the absence of fuel, D_{eff} is the effective diffusion coefficient in the presence of fuel and Δt is the time interval.

To investigate the propulsion mechanism of the nanomotor, 6.7 μL of 30% H_2O_2 were added to 1 mL of a 1 mg/mL $\text{NM}_{\text{CHX-F}}$ solution (final H_2O_2 concentration 0.2%), and a 3 min video was recorded. The dispersion dynamics of nanomotors population was evaluated by adding a drop of $\text{NM}_{\text{CHX-F}}$ (10 μL at a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) to 1 mL of PBS or PBS containing H_2O_2 (0.2 or 5%). Then, a 1 min video was recorded, and frames were captured at 0, 20, 40 and 60 s. The area occupied by the nanodevices and their spatial distribution (assessed through heat maps and pixel intensity within a region of interest defined by a rectangle extending from the addition point to the final positions reached by the nanomotors, covering the full diameter of the well) were analyzed using ImageJ.

3.7. Oral sample collection and biofilm growth

Saliva-derived biofilms: after approval from the University de València Ethics and Human Research Committee (registration number H1484736766706), unstimulated saliva samples were collected from six systemically healthy donors (≥ 18 years old) free of periodontal disease and active caries lesions. Saliva-derived biofilms were cultivated in liquid Brain Heart Infusion (BHI) medium (Biolife) supplemented with 2 mL/L vitamin K1 (V3501), 5 mg/L hemin, and 1 mg/L menadione (all from Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) [22]. Briefly, 150 μL of this medium were transferred into a 96-well flat-bottom plate wells (Ibidi, Germany, #89626). Subsequently, 150 μL of collected saliva samples from each donor were added to the corresponding wells, and biofilms were grown at 37 °C for 24 h. Following incubation, the 24 h biofilms were treated with H_2O_2 -activated nanoparticles ($\text{NM}_{\text{CHX-F}} + 0.15\% \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$) reaching 0.02% of CHX, non-activated nanoparticles ($\text{NM}_{\text{CHX-F}}$), 0.15% H_2O_2 , 0.02% CHX, and “unassembled device” (comprising all unassembled components used in nanoparticle synthesis plus 0.15% of H_2O_2). Biofilm growth continued for an additional 24 h after treatment. Endodontic biofilms: after approval from the University de València Ethics and Human Research Committee (registration number H1484736766706), endodontic biofilm samples were collected from six adult participants (≥ 18 years old) exhibiting negative cold sensitivity tests (verifying negative vitality by the absence of bleeding upon chamber access). Inclusion criteria ensured no recent antibiotic use, an intact crown without communication between the oral cavity and pulp chamber, and the absence of periodontal pockets (>4 mm), tooth mobility, or root fractures. Samples were collected into VMG III transport media without agar or agarose [51], and immediately transferred to

3.8. Crystal violet staining

Adhered biofilm biomass of both saliva and endodontic-derived biofilms was quantified using crystal violet (CV) staining as previously described [37,52]. Briefly, the culture supernatant was discarded, and both saliva and endodontic-derived biofilms were washed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH = 7.4) to eliminate non-adherent cells. A 0.1% CV solution was added to each well and incubated for 20 min. The CV solution was then removed, and the biofilms were rinsed with PBS to eliminate residual CV. Subsequently, the CV was then solubilized by adding 300 μL of 30% (v/v) glacial acetic acid and the optical density of the released CV was measured at 610 nm using a microplate reader (Tecan Infinite M200, Durham, NC, USA). Each experimental condition included four technical replicates along with corresponding negative controls.

3.9. LIVE/DEAD assay

The viability of saliva-derived biofilms was evaluated using a LIVE/DEAD assay. Samples were grown and treated for 24 h with $\text{NM}_{\text{CHX-F}}$ and H_2O_2 as described previously. Then, the supernatant was discarded, and biofilms were stained 200 μL of a solution of SYTO9 and propidium iodide (3 μL of each dye diluted in 1 mL of water) for 15 min in the dark. Finally, samples were washed with water and images were acquired by CLSM using a Leica TCS SP8 AOBS inverted laser scanning confocal. Fluorescence intensity was analyzed using ImageJ software. To determine the signal corresponding to viable cells, the red signal was subtracted from the green signal. Two random images per condition were analyzed.

3.10. EPS degradation and penetration assay

To evaluate the nanomotor ability to degrade EPS and penetrate the matrix of saliva-derived biofilms, the biofilms were labeled with Alexa Fluor 680-dextran conjugate. This fluorophore binds to *N*-acetyl neu-ramic acid and polysaccharide adhesin, which are involved in biofilm formation. Biofilms were grown and described previously, but in the presence of 0.13 mg/mL of Alexa Fluor 680-dextran conjugate and then treated with fluorescein-labeled nanomotors ($\text{NM}_{\text{FITC-CHX-F}}$) and H_2O_2 for 24 h. Subsequently, CLSM images were acquired as z-stacks (z-stack size: 5 μm) using a Leica TCS SP8 AOBS inverted laser scanning confocal, and 3D reconstructions were performed with LAS X 3D. Quantification of fluorescence intensity was carried out with ImageJ software.

3.11. *S. mutans* biofilm growth on dentine sections and viability counts

The research protocol was approved by the University of Granada Ethics Committee (UGR no. 438). Dentine blocks were prepared by sectioning non-carious freshly extracted teeth. After polishing (500–800 grade SiC papers), 2 × 2 × 1.2 mm specimens were obtained [2]. The dentine smear layer was demineralized using 17% EDTA for 4 min. The dentine blocks were then sterilized to create a standardized substrate for biofilm growth and kept in a sterile saline solution (pH = 7.4) at 4 °C until its use.

The sterilized dentine blocks were incubated in BHI growth medium containing approximately 1×10^7 colony-forming units per milliliter of *S. mutans* strain ATC25175 under anaerobic conditions at 37 °C for 7 days to facilitate biofilm formation. BHI medium was refreshed every 48

h. After a seven-day incubation period, mature *S. mutans* biofilms grown on the dentine surface were washed using a sterile saline solution to remove non-adherent bacterial cells. The biofilms were then treated with 50 μL of H_2O_2 -activated nanoparticles, non-activated nano-particles, 0.15% H_2O_2 , 0.2% CHX, and the corresponding unassembled device treatments for 1 and 5 min. After that, the biofilms were disrupted by sonication for 10 min in a sterile saline solution. The resulting bacterial suspensions were then serially diluted and plated for colony counting to assess biofilm viability. Plates were incubated for approximately 48 h in anaerobic conditions

at 37 °C, and colony-forming units (CFUs) were counted, averaged, and expressed as log₁₀ CFU/mL. Seven replicates per condition were included.

3.12. Intratubular *S. mutans* biofilm infection model

A previously described protocol was used for dentine specimen preparation and infection with *S. mutans* [24]. Briefly, cylindrical root segments (4 mm length) were obtained from freshly extracted single rooted teeth by horizontally sectioning the root 1 mm below the cemento-enamel junction using an Accuton-50 machine (Struers, Copenhagen, Denmark). These segments were further halved using a low-speed handpiece equipped with a diamond disk (355,514,220 HP; Edenta AG, AU/St Gallen, Switzerland). The outer dentine of each half-section was then removed to obtain specimens with dimensions of 4 × 4 × 2 mm. To remove the smear layer generated during preparation, specimens were treated with 17% EDTA for 5 min followed by a 10 min wash with distilled water. Subsequently, the specimens were sterilized using autoclaving.

Each sterilized dentine specimen was placed in the upper chamber of a sterile filter tube (VWR International Eurolab SL, Barcelona, Spain) with the canal orifice facing upwards. Gaps between the specimen and the inner tube wall were sealed with flowable composite resin (Tetric EvoFlow; Ivoclar Vivadent, Schaan, Liechtenstein) and light-cured for 20 s. A freshly fresh suspension of 500 µL of *S. mutans* ATCC25175 in BHI (approximately 1 × 10⁷ CFU/mL) was added to the upper chamber of each filter tube containing the dentine specimen. The tubes were then centrifuged sequentially at increasing centrifugal forces (1400 xg, 2000 xg, 3600 xg, and 5000 xg) for two 5-min cycles at each force. Following each centrifugation step, the bacterial suspension was replaced with a fresh 500 µL aliquot containing 1 × 10⁷ CFU/mL. This centrifugation was repeated 48 h later. The infected dentine specimens were incubated for a total of seven days at 37 °C, with media changes every 48 h. After the incubation period, the specimens were retrieved from the tubes, washed with sterile saline solution, treated with the corresponding treatments for 5 min as described above and further processed by cutting specimens into halves. Seven replicates per condition were included.

For observation under CLSM, the dentine specimens were stained with the LIVE/DEAD BacLight viability kit (Invitrogen, Eugene, OR, USA) containing Syto-9 and propidium iodide dyes for 15 min, as recommended by the manufacturer. Following staining, the dentine samples were rinsed with saline solution and observed using CLSM (TCS-SP5 II; Leica, Wetzlar, Germany). Confocal volumes were acquired from each sample using a 40× oil immersion lens, with a step size of 1 µm and a format of 512 × 512 pixels. Each image represented an area of 387.5 ×

387.5 µm. Nikon software (NIS Elements Imaging Software, version 3.0 SP7) was then used to reconstruct the 3D structures of the biofilms.

Additional dentine specimens cultured with fully-grown *S. mutans* biofilms were treated with the NM_{CHX-F} + H₂O₂ for 5 min for SEM visualization of the nanoparticles inside the dentinal tubules. Thereafter, the halves of the treated coronal segments were separated, fixed in 2.5% glutaraldehyde, desiccated, sputter-coated with carbon, and observed under a dual-beam Focused Ion Beam Scanning Electron Microscope (FIB-SEM, AMBER X, TESCAN). For the nanomotor's platinum observation, the backscattered electron detection was used and EDX spectroscopy was performed.

3.13. Statistical analysis

Student's *t*-tests were performed to identify statistical differences between treatments, *p* < 0.05 was considered significant. Asterisks indicate significance (* *p* < 0.05, ** *p* < 0.01, *** *p* < 0.001, **** *p* < 0.0001). Non-significant differences are indicated as ns.

Ethics and consent to participate declarations

Not applicable.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors are the inventors of a patent application protecting the use of nanomotors to combat biofilm-mediated diseases, whose owners are the Polytechnic University of Valencia and the FISABIO Foundation.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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